

Linguistic Landscape in Indonesian Restaurant Signages: Meanings in the Use of English, Color Selection and Neon Boxes

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Abstract

English in Indonesia has been perceived as a modern language and one carrying prestige for Indonesian users, despite that English has never been its second language. Its use is more widely spread with the increase number of businesses, including the vast grow of eateries and restaurants in recent years. Therefore, this study was conducted to validate the use of English, in particular, and the use of its counterparts and to discover the colors used, and to find out whether the use of neon boxes has a connection with the accentuation of the meanings in association to English as the language of modernity and of prestige. To make the data distinctive, the restaurants and cafes chosen are those hosting international tourists. With the application of multimodality, this research discovers the meanings implied in the 7 (seven) selected restaurant and cafe signages in 3 (three) selected cities and a town in Jawa Timur province in Indonesia. The result proves that English is the dominant language used both as the brand names and the classifier to show the type of restaurants or cafes the signages address. However, among the seven eating places, there are 1 (one) restaurant uses Indonesian-Dutch language and 1 (one) Indochinese language and 1 (one) Indonesian language, containing a meaning of the menu served. There are 6 (six) out of 7 (seven) signages use neon boxes, which are likely to be associated with modernity and prestige, while the one that does not use a neon box indicates populism, which means affordable prices and its target customers are common people. In sum, the use of English, color selection, and neon boxes in some ways work hand in hand to create modernity and prestige.

Keywords: English, signage, linguistic landscape, modernity, prestige

INTRODUCTION

English is a global language, a marker of globalization (Kasanga, 2010 in Taylor-Leech, 2011), 'the indisputable world language' (Dörnyei, Csizér and Németh 2006, in Carrie 2016:1-2). These English words or their recontextualized ones eventually become part of the local repertoires, signifying that globalization has been spread over the place (Lanza and Woldemariam, 2017). Concomitant with the advanced technology development that initially started from the English-speaking countries, in particular the US, alongside with the advent of culture and product of culture, as well as economy growth, more public signs have been posted and more English terms have been coined. The more visual information has been produced recently, the more signs are made than ever before (Backhaus, 2019; Gorter and Cenoz, 2007). Public signs nowadays increase in number and these signs mainly contain more languages, especially English involved, as well as have more diverse materials and colors. Each item, what so-called mode, mentioned has affordances important to build coherence and meaning making (Bezemer and Kress, 2008; Blommaert, 2013; Kress, 2010).

Many researches in the last 3 decades put some great interests on seeing linguistic phenomenon in public signs in a territory, later known as Linguistic Landscape (henceforth: LL). The term emanated from Landry and Bourhis' work in 1997. They argued public signs do not only pose as of distinctive markers but of transactional communication among public as well. From that time onward, more researches scrutinize the use of English and other language in a multicultural context in relation to the globalization, identities and values generated from its use (Coluzzi, 2012; Jeng and Luo, 2019; Lanza and Woldemariam, 2013; Li, 2015, Lowenberg, 1991; Rowland, 2015). Not only the language, the non-language entities like space, time, the domain are investigated as well (Blommaert, 2013; Ghouma, 2016; 'Geosemiotics' by Scollon and Wong Scollon, 2003). Gorter (2013) even alluded that the LL's research coverage is broad, including multilingualism (Albury, 2018; Gorter and Cenoz, 2015; Prasert and Zilli, 2019; Prasert, Keerati and Zili, 2019, Taylor-leech, 2011), multimodality, language diversity, and minority language (Coluzzi, 2012).

Those investigations on LL mostly share something in common, in particular, observing English as part of the elements in the public signs, apart from those local or other minority languages in the context of multilingual world. In addition, language indexing identity is indeed abundant. With sociological, cultural, sociolinguistic and political properties behind the signs constructed, reasons can be revealed (Blommaert, 2013; Bezemer, et al., 2019, Kress, 2010). Likewise, research on multimodality and translation used in the signs are conducted by few

researches such as Chen, 2016; Seals, 2017; while, Al Naimat and Alomoush on materiality (2019). Eventhough LL has been recently quite popular, LL researches in Indonesia are still few, and these include LL along public places and main streets in Sidoarjo-Indonesia by Fakhroh and Rohmah (2018) and LL in senior high schools in Yogyakarta (Andriyanti, 2019). Due to rarity of the LL researches in Indonesia, and rarity of an LL research alluded neon boxes or illuminated signages, it might be crucial to analyse those discuss text in signages mostly dominated with English and its counterparts and the use of neon boxes in selected local area. As more public signs are found and with the increasing number of culinary business, this research focuses on signages of restaurants and cafes and the use colors and of the illuminated signages in Indonesia, in particular Jawa Timur province, to decipher any social, cultural, economic or political functions behind the signs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Linguistic Landscape and Multilingualism

Linguistic landscape (LL) was a term introduced by Landry and Bourhis (1997) pinpointing how language is visibly made use as public signs in a particular territory or area. This sign is believed to contain information and symbolic functions that have something to do with the relative power and status of a particular community in the related territory. Gorter and Cenoz (2007:4) reiterated that the symbolic function indexes the perception that the language users have that value and status as compared to other language. With the notion of ethnolinguistic vitality, they revealed that there was a correlation between the latter with the perceptions of the vitality of the in-group language and a relation to show the effect of the linguistic landscape on language behavior. LL views public signs as characteristics of the language community where the signs are located (Backhaus, 2019; Bourhis, 1992 in Landry and Bourhis 1997). As languages used in a territory are rarely homogenous, LL can provide us information on sociolinguistic compositions in the territory (1997).

LL's coverage is very broad too, in terms of innovative theoretical and empirical studies dealing with issues on multilingualism, literacy, multimodality, language policy, linguistic diversity and minority languages, among others (Gorter, 2013: 190). Gorter argue that LL was already multilingual compelled by globalization, marked by the penetration of foreign brand names and other names of socio-cultural and ideological products from English speaking countries into non-English-speaking ones. The use of language in the public space is the main focus of LL (2013:191). The spread of multilingualism involves globalization (Alomoush, 2018; Lanza and Woldemariam, 2013; Rowland, 2015), immigration, the revitalization of minority

languages and tourism, and cultural and linguistic diversity. LL has two categories is the top-down which is 'government' or official signs for street names, and the bottom-up signs that are private signs that may be influenced by the language policy (Ben-Rafael, et al., 2006). The last is language policy, this is closely related to Landry and Bourhis' symbolic functions as defined by Gorter and Cenoz (2007). Based on what Ben-Rafael, et al. observed, LL items was not totally about typical ethnographic diversity, it is more like individual and institutional choices as symbolic construction which lies on 3 different factors: rationale, presentation of self and power relations. These first two are made use in this article, as power relations are hard to see in these small numbers of data.

English, Modernity and Typical Indonesian English

Like other foreign languages came earlier, English in Indonesia permeated in Indonesia through language policy. Taught hand in hand with Dutch during Dutch colonization, English soon replaced Dutch as the foreign language widely taught throughout the nation. The spread of English flourished as it became the primary international medium and as it is the lingua franca of Indonesia's neighboring countries. English has been more established due to extensive financial and material support and exchanging programs from the U.S. (Douglas, 1970 in Lowenberg, 1991) and had been rapidly growing in number of users as it is the global language and similar to what English' counterpart -Dutch- which came earlier to Indonesia. Indonesians speaking English are recognized as educated people or those from high society (Tanner, 1967 in Lowenberg, 1991).

It has a significant impact on language use in Indonesia, particularly through lexicosemantic and pragmatic contributions to Indonesian (Lowenberg, 1991:127). English borrowings, he further stated, are often frequently extended, restricted, or totally shifted to provide new registers for Indonesian, to foreground a modern identity for educated urbanites and for those who aspire to be like them, and to express or neutralize new values and behavior patterns in Indonesia's rapidly modernizing society. However, English in Indonesia has given a major impact on lexicalization, rather on its function as a communication medium, unlike her adjacent counterparts, such a Singapore, Malaysia and the Phillipines. Lowenberg then suggested English lexical items creating new registers associated with modernity in Indonesia. English in Indonesia had proven to be loanwords obtained either officially or spontaneously to neutralize the connoted Indonesian words, to be used in particular register, and to be as of a marker for its speakers' identity.

Multimodality: Modes, Interaction, Context, and Globalization

Any texts, colors, others, used for communicative purposes are modes. Modes are semiotic resources for meaning making which are socially and culturally constructed, that have potentials and limitations called as semiotic affordances (Kress, 2010). The semiotic system constructed is tightly connected the negotiation between the local forms and traditions with features outside the locality encapsulated on arrangements and dispositions of power in a locality (Kress, 2010). In visual communication when non-verbal signs involved, resources or modes are made use to build and continue the interaction between the producer and the viewer of the image. Kress and van Leeuwen (2006) argued that there are represented participants – or anything depicted in images – and interactive participants – ones mentioned earlier. These interactive participants are real persons involved in images meaning making under a particular social and cultural context to construct and to read what is supposed to be said in the images, as well as in terms of how these should be expressed and interpreted. In this, the interaction may be either direct (face to face) or indirect (be it the producer or viewer is not present). The latter enables the producer tailor a mental image of the viewer, or the viewer envisages the meaning of the images with the absence of the producer. The interaction occur between these two comes to realize by what so-called interpersonal function where the producer, expounded by Halliday and Matthiessen (2004) has two roles in exchange, explained in details as follows:

Table 1. speech functions [adopted from Halliday and Matthiessen, 2004].

In advertising, the function of language predominantly employs interpersonal function, in a way that the producers of the advertisements articulate the voices of the owner of the product or service. The modes used are intended to offer the prospective customers, in particular invite them to receive the commodity either goods-&-services or information, and they invite them to give in return. Mostly, restaurants do not deploy human in their signages, indicating that no direct eye contact is made, thus it is meant to offer the represented participants as object to contemplate (Kress and van Leeuwen, 2006).

METHODOLOGY

This research is qualitative research, since the research does not analyze numerical data, but the pictures of signages of restaurants and or eateries which comprise linguistic text and visual features in them. Thus, the data lie on modes in Indonesian restaurant signages both using English only and English and its counterparts and or English counterparts only, that also comprise color selection used as well as whether the signs are illuminated or not and what is conceived in the selections made. The restaurants and eateries chosen were in 3 (three) chosen towns in Jawa Timur province. The photos of these signages were taken during January to February 2020. The first data were pictures of signages of restaurants/eateries in Surabaya.

These restaurants and or eateries chosen were those reported to be the 7 most visited restaurants by international tourists. The second were those of 6 restaurants in Malang seen to serve international visitors and some reported to be most visited by the visitors. The last data were 2 eateries in Jember recommended for hosting international tourists to Jember. Thus, these 16 restaurants and cafes signages were collected, most of which making use of English, in particular, and using its counterparts (Indonesian and or other local languages), and few of which using Indonesian only and or other languages, and these exclude those situated in the restaurants inside hotels. Due to some facts that international tourists are mostly invited to have dinner along with the hosts and due to the increasing number of neon boxes in Indonesia, the data taken were signages shot at dusk and evening. Therefore, only 7 (seven) data were analyzed due to the relevance and representativeness. In addition, restaurant and eateries are the most favorite destinations to hang out or to dine out for a more intimate or romantic outing, either for business or intimate purposes. This approach generally involves explorations of the intention of signage producers, the interpretations of signage readers, and/or the multimodal features and physical emplacement of signage, as a way of revealing the complex interactions between people, signage, space and time (Blommaert, 2013; Gorter 2013 in Rowland 2015); and, mass-scale event using multimodality (Seals, 2017). In addition, information about types of signages are taken from Anderson (2018) and other websites as listed in the references and colors interpretation is not basically based on the meaning of each distinctive color, but the meanings in their functions, in relation to the context surrounds as mentioned previously. The linguistic texts were analyzed using Halliday's nominal group. To help understand what kinds of restaurants or eateries scrutinized, features inside the restaurants, including the menu and indoor room designs were important to decipher, and the information were partly obtained through <https://pergikuliner.com/restaurants/> as interviews are not likely to happen, due to the situation when economy suffers amidst the corona pandemic.

CONTEXT

The following is the details of the context involved that helps assist the analysis of the modes in the public signs. The context meant comprises the description of the selected cities, the short history of the emergence of English and its spreading in Indonesia, and lastly but not least, the signages materials, especially the advent of neon boxes which seemingly becomes a trend in Indonesia for the last ten years.

To decipher the meanings behind the modes in the selected signages, understanding contexts is necessary. First, the geographical domains of where the signages were located should be presented. The typical cities where the chosen public signs were located are described as follows: (1) Surabaya – famous for its business, there live expatriates (businessmen, educators, academicians, and consulate officials) and its historical landmark; (2) Malang – famous for, in particular, its domestic tourist spots; (3) Jember – a growing city where I live. This is a bit crowded place and has been internationally-recognized as the city of carnival hold in the last decade.

Apart from the types of cities which may affect the type of the public signs, understanding how English first time appeared in Indonesia is a pivotal thing to know. English in Indonesia was firstly taught to few Indonesian students of those in junior and senior high schools during the Dutch occupancy, but was temporarily prohibited to teach during the Japanese invasion. For the first time after Indonesia got her independence's day, it was officially taught throughout Indonesia, following the decree of the Ministry of Education and Culture of 1967 (speakot.palcomtech.com/844/). Since then, English has become one and only foreign language that is widely taught and mostly used in education and business and tourism. However, for almost more than 5 decades since it was ubiquitously learnt and used, English language proficiency index of Indonesia is at the rank of 51 out of 88 countries of worldwide (<https://www.ef.co.id/epi/about-epi/>) and is considered as one has low proficiency. Given that English is not well mastered by most Indonesians, its use has been preferably favorited for decades, apart from there were some period of times when frantic attempts were made by the governments to decrease the wildly growing influences of English in businesses, with some frontal suggestion to change English-sounding names with more local names under the era of Soekarno and Soeharto, such as 'Plaza Sarinah' came to exist among the trend of using English names for Plazas in Jakarta in Soekarno's era; and in 1990s 'Delta Plaza' was changed into 'Plaza Surabaya', Tunjungan Plaza into 'Plaza Tunjungan' and 'Studio East' into 'Studio Etan' ('Etan' - 'wetan' is the local language for 'east' - due to similar 'nationality' courage. Nevertheless, this English naming trend has started to stand out within the last two decades. One phenomenon indicating the trend lies on shop front signage.

The use of neon boxes in some - if not most - signages recently in Indonesia raises a question: do neon boxes contribute to the overall meanings implied in the signages of the restaurants or eateries in Indonesia and do these relate to meaning of the use of English in the Indonesian signages? These two questions come up with the idea that most signages in pricy restaurants use neon boxes. Tracing back to years back then, shop front signages in Indonesia

were not that multimodal as those in developed countries and as those in early 1990s up to the present. Neon-boxes, for example, presumably have been popular in small towns in Indonesia in 2000s. These multimodalities can be seen in both the diverse materials and more than one language used, pertinent to the advance of the current technology (Cenoz, et al., 2017:234). The use of non-vernacular language, especially English, has been seemingly increasing not only in Jakarta, the capital city, but also in some cities and towns in Indonesia. This is due to the penetration of international brand names, apart from that of English to non-English speaking countries (Cenoz, et al., 2017:234). Thus, English along with local languages and or with other languages and other multimodal entities altogether have increasingly embellished the shop front signages. Eventually, this is to discover how the modes used successfully represent either the identity or purposes of the signages, as suggested by Lowenberg whose research was about the use of English in Indonesia.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

As public signages apply multimodality, it is essential to construe both the linguistic and visual elements in the signs. The linguistic element includes words, phrases, or clauses that were scrutinized using language visibility and the connotative meanings implied in the usage. Meanwhile, the visual element contains the non-linguistic signs that contribute to the meaning intended to convey. The visual communication involves resources of executing and maintaining a kind of interaction between the producers and the viewer of the image Kress and van Leeuwen (2006). The digest of the result of the overall analysis is tabulated in the table below:

Table. The Result of the Multimodal Texts in the Selected Restaurants and Eateries

Location	No	Names of Restaurants/Eateries	of
Surabaya	1.	De Soematra 1910	Dutch-designed building and a special text of Indonesian-Dutch language with Dutch language structure manifested in illuminated signage.
	2.	Dream of Kahyangan art resto	The restaurant's name suggests a blend of Indonesian (particularly, Javanese) – English languages, while the emblem or the type of business is written in English: art resto. From the selection of Javanese word and Chinese's

			nuance of red color, this restaurant offers Javanese and Chinese menu.
Malang	3	Kertanegara Indonesian Restaurant	The name of the restaurant and its type of business indicates Indonesian Javanese culture in the form of menu is served. The Chinese vibe is seen through the color selection, which is red orange. The word 'Halal' is added to welcome muslim (potential) customers. With its big illuminated signage in the area where luxurious shops, restaurants and houses are located, it implies that this restaurant offers not quite affordable price of foods and drinks.
	4	Public, social drinkery and kitchen	Both the name and the type of business of this restaurant are in English. The label 'social drinkery' presumably implies the polite term for alcoholic beverages. The illuminated neon box and the color selection indicate elegance, simplicity, making the place modern and elegant as well as high-end.
	5	Saigonsan Modern Vietnamese and Thai	Saigonsan is derived from 'Saigon' the former name of the capital city of Vietnam. The name of this restaurant suggests what kinds of foods offered. This is proven by the type of business 'Modern Vietnamese and Thai' decrypted in the signage. The orange-red-yellow namely as goldenrod color signifies the Chinese culture, while the illuminated neon box leaves us impressions of mundane and modern, as well as high-end.
Jember	6	Grand Café Café and Eatery	Grand café is likely to mean grand in terms of varies menu and or wide business, while the classifer, coffee and eatery, is referred to the menu and prices are offered. The illuminated neon box indexes modernity, salience.
	7	<i>Kafe Kolong</i>	<i>Kafe Kolong</i> is an Indonesian term. 'Kafe' is adopted from English, it means it is bigger than a café which is not as big as a restaurant.

It offers a cozy vibe and modernity. Unlike other discussed signages, this sign has a dark nuance and non-illuminated sign bring a different appearance of what the restaurant looks like.

The following is the mapping of the linguistic landscape of three cities, reading characters of restaurant signages of each of them to acknowledge how English intersects with others and other meaning resources made use, as well as how branding is performed in the scope of LL.

THE LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE OF SURABAYA

English and non-English usage in Restaurant Signages

Surabaya inherits the remnants of Dutch colonization, as seen on the city where visitors will easily find remarkably Dutch-designed and other historical buildings. The current trend of restaurant business that was observe is the increasing number of old buildings converted into restaurants. Not only the architecture is utilized, the blend of Indonesian-Dutch names is also made use, which is then perceived as one classy-classic restaurant with high quality food, and inevitably, expensive (see figure 1). During Dutch occupation, Dutch or white people were considered people with high-end class and so are their food likings. The choice of other meaning resources we can see from the art of the illumination and colors the signage of the restaurant performs adjoins the impression of a high class and modern restaurant, enhancing the salience of the restaurant with contrast colors of white (ivory) and black, making it visible to viewers [to speed visual search] passing by.

Figure 1. De Soematra 1910, using Indonesian with Dutch-spelling system reminiscing a colonization era

Another type of names of restaurant found in Surabaya is one combining English and Indonesian. Dream of Kahyangan art resto, as its name suggested, implies particular products this place offers. 'Dream' conceives thoughts, images, minds but with a positive vibe, unlike the word 'nightmare'; whereas 'Kahyangan' (derived from Sanskrit and adopted by Javanese and also recognized in Indonesian) means an Eden, or Nirvana in Hinduism. These two are visualized with the existence of the image of clouds under. The next is art Resto is the classifier (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004), as the emblem. Undeniably, the word 'restaurant' has been adopted to be Indonesian, and works as the classifier of any place representing as it is, and 'art' is a word indexing to a design. The presupposition on people's minds that this place has a remarkably unique design inside. The colors selected remind us to the color of nature for green as seen on the classifier 'art resto', and the color of Chinese descent Indonesian for red color on 'dream of Kahyangan'. In this way, the colors function not only as an easy access for viewers to find the place, it is also to enhance meaning of the place, and to denote an identity as one related to Chinese and Javanese, and the lighting is for sure to make it a modern and visible place to visit.

Figure 2. A restaurant offering a uniquely-designed place in Surabaya

Branding in the Linguistic Landscape in Surabaya

Similar to other languages, branding of restaurant signages in Surabaya evidently hinted globalization through penetration of English words and structure, including Dutch structure similar to English structure. Fine-dining and casual restaurants with more varied and distinctive names, not only making use of English and Indonesian, but also of other languages especially Dutch, or French, Chinese, or Italian. These are found in several restaurant names, known to be most favorited places for white people or international tourists, especially expatriats in the business city of Surabaya which was formerly colonized by the Netherlands. These backgrounds shape the modern Surabaya. In this, it was tacitly noticed the increasing number of multilingual people coming in, to surf the one of a kind restaurant, offering scrumptious taste and unique ambiance. Colors and illumination are resources to enhance the branding, including to make them conspicuous and modern-like. Through branding, offer and demand are initiations the producers deploy (Kress and van Leeuwen, 2006) as well as a part of interaction happen between these two parties as part of the practice of interpersonal function of language (Halliday and Matthiessen, 2004).

THE LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE OF MALANG

English and non-English usage in Restaurant Signages

Malang is the second biggest city in Jawa Timur province, and has been the most favorite domestic tourist spot, yet some international tourists are reported to visit this city, known as the icon of the apple city, as this area is a fertile land for apple trees. In the Socio-

cultural point of view, Malang is closely connected historically to two distinct governances: first is it was rooted to its Hindu-Buddha Javanese kingdom, and second it was used to be a garrison town in the era of Dutch colonization. These become the bases of the restaurant naming in Malang. One apparent example is that in Figure 3. 'Kertanegara' and Indonesian Restaurant and the word 'halal' in Arabic and phone number together with its illuminated red and yellow coloring neon box. Kertanegara, as its name suggested, the indigenous identity of the place's name, of that recalling readers of the Javanese culture of an ancient Javanese kingdom 'Singhasari' with its famous king's name "Kertanegara", indicates locality of Javanese value and identity, as a restaurant selling local cuisines, which probably conceive a notion of that of reasonable prices. However, this assumption is totally wrong when seeing where the restaurant is and the material of the signage. It positions itself as restaurant with international standard, as if summoning for international visitors to drop by and dine in while at the same time it promotes local identity of selling Indonesian foods. The 'halal' issue legitimates it as its side value, to call for local tourists who may dine in there with relief as part of their religious belief satisfaction. This signage of this restaurant altogether constructs a meaning that this local restaurant [identity] selling Indonesian foods [meaning], serves visitors with an indigenous culture design, without lessening its standard to welcome international visitors, represented in the use of English and the use of illuminated neon boxes to make it stand out or modern-like. Apart from illuminated and contrastive colors selection enhancing the place and enabling people for easy search, yellow and red coloring in its box imply identity, that the owner might be possibly a Chinese-descent, on one hand and on the other hand, this sells Indonesian as well as Asian foods. From the linguistic code, 'Kertanegara' as the Thing (core) classified as Indonesian restaurant, and like other Indonesian signages, English words seem to become elements embodied in every public sign meant to promote products and associate them with modernity.

Figure 3. A Restaurant using Local name offering local nuance in Malang

Figure 4 displays a restaurant signage uses fully English. Public, social drinkery and kitchen looks so mundane and modern, with both the Thing (the restaurant's name) and the classifier both use English. Public, as its name suggests, may be intended to call for visitors to come in and enjoy their time hanging out in there. English has been acknowledged to be the language of those elite users and brought up the pride for its users and consumers (Lowenberg, 1991), and this marks the globalization where multilingual people might be around the corner. Moreover, the classifier following the name, social drinkery, is referred to a public place selling liquors and kitchen selling foods of more varied 'global' cuisines. The color selection is another thing which makes the place eye catching, elegant, simple, high-end, constructing the identity of the place as modern and elegance.

Figure 4. No local nuance found in this restaurant signage in Malang

Figure 5 shows an Indochina restaurant, Saigonsan. 'Saigonsan' (the Thing) is that of non English, emanated from Indochina language. This is one of a kind restaurant among commonly found ones of those Japanese, Chinese, and European in Malang. Saigonsan offers a special menu of Indochina cuisines and room design, as reflected in the classifier using English 'Modern Vietnamese and Thai'. Apart from making the signs standing out from the crowd, English use is the other thing to woo the public. Lowenberg (1991) reported that English loans have a certain prestige for its users even these users hardly know English. The orange-red-yellow namely as goldenrod color reminisces us to the Chinese-related rationale behind its use in the signage of this restaurant. The illuminated neon box leaves us impressions of mundane and modern, as well as high-end one with surely non reasonable prices they charge, even the linguistic feature says so 'modern'. Similarly, like other color selection function, these may make the restaurant distinctive, easy to recognize, easy to reach.

Figure 5. An Indochina nuance restaurant in Malang

Branding in the Linguistic Landscape in Malang

The restaurant outdoor signages in Malang were made to advertise the brand, when the producers attempt to interact with the prospective visitors by initiating to offer the commodity both the goods and service and information and to demand the passing viewers' attention to drop by. In addition, this entices customers, inviting them to give and receive their commodity though creating curiosity and encouraging them to dine in, making them impressed and felt like they have found the right place, displayed in some signages with more contrastive color selection, so that the invisible onlookers engaged with the colors displayed and distinctive names and menus implied in both the name and classifier. In this way, viewers can recognize and identify the place, to decide to drop by soon and or to contemplate and decide to visit it later. The varied languages and designs in casual and ethnic restaurants in Malang signify a notion that there is a presence of international or multilingual people visiting this second largest city in Jawa Timur province.

THE LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE OF JEMBER

English and non-English usage in Restaurant Signages

Jember is a town not as big as either Surabaya or Malang. It is a growing town and recently famous for its annual city carnival. Unlike Surabaya and Malang known to be most

visited cities by international tourists, Jember has fewer as reported to visit the place. In fact, it is the fifth town in Jawa Timur province to be the destination for international tourists (Syafira, 2024). The main languages are found in the restaurant signages are Indonesian/local and English. The rest is Japanese and Korean, since the last two have not been reported to be visited by international tourists, these are left unanalyzed. The use of English in Indonesia is tightly connected to globalization, leading to glocalization. Lowenberg (1991) had reported that English is associated with one bringing a new concept different from that of the prior one and this is also considered as symbol of modernity and leaves an impression of having intellectual elite for its users. Among those restaurant signages found, if not as the nominal group functioning as the Thing, the English wordings are used as the Classifier, a particular subclass of the Thing (Halliday and Matthiessen, 2004). Grand café as a Thing implies this café is grand, great, in terms of that it is a wide place or it has varies menu or in terms of that it is a wide business, that include café business and cellphone business. The classifier, coffee and eatery (figure 6), is a clear example of what is implied in the menu and prices charged. This means that the prices offered are affordable. This is due to the fact that Jember is a budget-conscious market. The use of English is for sure as the result of English penetration to Indonesia, and has been long adopted to index a new concept, and (non-local) menu in our culture. Thus, Grand café adopts English for both the effectiveness and the modernity it conceives. Colors and illuminated neon boxes have been proved to make the café as well as eatery stand out, distinctive, so that it is easy to reach and recognize.

Figure 6. This café is the favorite place for local guide to welcome international tourists

In another café found in Jember, local name is preferred (figure 7). However, this local name does sounds very local, due to the use of the loanword 'kafe'. Lowenberg (1991) claimed that English in Indonesia is used in the form lexical items. An English word adopted and adjusted with the Indonesian ortography 'Kafe' (originated from English 'café'), for instance, has a different meaning from that of its Indonesian counterparts, like 'warung' (small restaurant) and 'kedai' (coffeehouse). In comparison with 'warung' and 'kedai', 'Kafe' has another trait, that is 'modern' and has a cozy vibe. The signage this café offers, unlike most signages discussed, has a noir background. Dark nuance and non-illuminated sign bring a different appearance of what the restaurant looks like. The colors selected give different vibes too, compared to other restaurants discussed. For symbolism and identity construction, 'kafe kolong' (which is literally translated into a café in an underpass) has a unique design as it is situated under a bridge. The café is 'populist' and reasonable price, for it is located under the bridge, serves the visitors of different look of common eatery and café.

Figure 7. a unique, noir café, serving visitors of a rare sensation of under-the bridge cafe

Branding in the Linguistic Landscape in Jember

There are less variations of languages and signages especially in restaurants or cafes or eateries visited by international tourists in this growing town in comparison with variations in the two discussed cities previously. There were two restaurants reported to be most visited ones by international tourists, and this is because the local guides direct them to drop by. The

use of English here proves to be one providing us with non-local menu, and conceives pride and prestige, and even used for people who do not know English well (Lowenberg, 1991). The signages, in the same way of those of other restaurants, particularly the type of the eating place are meant to advertise the commodity and to attract the viewers and engage them with particular identity, so that it is recognizable.

DISCUSSION

The research on LL is not merely about ethnographic features that are tightly connected to the locality the place has. From the findings, it can be drawn into a conclusion that what Ben-Rafael, et al. fourteen years ago argued is still up to date, as they reported that English is widely used and independent from any local linguistic phenomena. They are in fact closely related to symbols of individual and institutional choices they make for public sphere, and expressions of particular identity they construct and or they promote. For bottom-up signages, rather than reflecting the dominant culture, these are free choices or individual strategies (Ben-Rafael, et al., 2006). These selections contribute to meanings, and consequently, particular forms are handpicked. In this, multimodality helps to shed light on meaning revelation of chosen modes, that behind the modes, the producers and the viewers or prospective visitors conduct an interaction (Ben-Rafael, et al, 2006; Scollon and Scollon, 2003). From the advertising, the producers offer and demand their commodity both the goods and services their restaurants have, and information left. The modes selection conceives a notion that the signages are made to advertise [the producers' side], to entice the customers [the producers' side], and as recognition [the viewers' side]. Colors are used not for its individual distinctive color per se, but mainly for their functions comprising: for speed visual search, to improve object recognition, to enhance meaning, to establish identity, and for symbolism. Whilst, illuminated and non-illuminated have something to do with salience and modern at the most.

Multimodality helps assist readers to decipher meanings conceived in the signages. It is based on an idea that all communication is multimodal, meaning communication makes use of more than one modes in one social event. For instance, a presentation combines spoken language, written text, colors, images, and body language to construct an intended meaning. The 7 (seven) selected signages accentuate the use of English particularly as classifier to the 6 out of 7 restaurants and an eatery. Among the 7 eating places, the 2 (two) restaurants and 1 (one) cafe use Indonesian as the brand name, and 1 (one) restaurant uses Indonesian but with

a typical Dutch phrase structure, and another restaurant uses an Indochinese name. there are 6 (six) out of 7 (seven) restaurants that use English as the classifier, to exhibit the type of restaurant or food they offer. These indicate that English is the most visible language in comparison with its counterparts. For decades, English remains to be believed as showing modernity, and prestige, as well as in some ways it means luxury (high-priced), that only belong to educated people. In addition, color selection in some ways indexes cultural meaning, especially in Chinese or Chinese-related restaurants or menus, which are found in 3 (three) out of 7 (seven) restaurants and an eatery. The color of beige seems to represent modernity. These all are enhanced by the use of illuminated neon boxes in which the signages are displayed. There is only one signage which is not a neon box, thus not illuminated, that implies populism, meaning that the prices offered are affordable.

CONCLUSION

From time to time, English has constructed the meaning of modern and prestige with its persistent existence in almost every signage found. Even though English words are not always applicable in its brand name, this foreign language stays firm as classifier of that what type of the restaurant or what to serve in the restaurants/eateries. The use of languages predominantly implies the design and type of menu offered – English use is for a broad menu, both local and non-local ones- and while the non-English and local language use may give readers a presupposition of serving them with the language-related menu, such as Indochinese menu uses Indochinese name or its associated names. The only Arabic found is recognized to be a more narrowed purpose, as as a legitimate label for muslim visitors to dine in, a non Muslim – Chinese -descent - restaurant. Apart from the use of English which is associated with modernity and prestige, the use of neon boxes underpin the impression English has. So, these two work hand in hand to create such effects.

These findings are expected to be more valid when more data can be collected and analyzed in the future. The abundance of data will help map the overall depiction of the use of English and its counterparts and the use of neon boxes in these three selected cities and town and will validate the findings. However, as Ben-Rafael, et al. (2006) suggested that bottom-up signs are concerned with personal choices, therefore it can be concluded that exceptions to the general findings—such as cafes offering affordable prices and the use of English being associated with high-priced offerings— may occur. Eventually, it is expected that the findings of this research can serve as a relevant basis for more extensive studies in the near future.

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